

A Study on Effective Learning Practices of IT Employees at Bengaluru

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Abstract

Learning is considered as an integral part for individual development. In today's environment learning happens from cradle to grave. From the year 1990, Peter Senge (Fifth Discipline) industries (corporate) were gazing at learning as a part for development of workplace and device new ideas for changing customer needs. As far as learning is concerned, there are many forms of learning for knowledge development and reusing in the society for development. There are some kinds of knowledge like tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge, which are used by human beings. Some kinds of learning process can be codified and captured for assessment, but there are certain forms of knowledge that cannot be captured or transformed.

Moreover, Learning has been classified into formal learning and informal learning. Earlier times, formal learning means which is provided in schools and colleges. Now formal learning happens at workplace because of various reasons like technological development and changing customer needs. This study mainly concentrates on the area of corporate or workplace learning. There are many types of learning that happens at the workplace, this particular study focuses mainly on five types of learning that happens at the workplace like Project learning, Peer learning, Research Learning, Incidental Learning and Hands-on learning.

Keywords: IT (information technology), Peer learning, formal learning, Research Learning and informal learning.

Introduction

In current day's Knowledge Economy, Learning happens to be an integral and intrinsic proficiency required by a company that aspires to grow and survive in their specific industry. Keeping in mind, the Competitive advantage and corporate learning, many firms attain sustainability and growth within the current competitive corporate scenario. Corporate learning enables the organizations to reciprocate efficiently and accustom to the uncertain corporate scenario. Organizational Learning is a combination of self-

learning, culture amelioration, constant advancement, innovation and enforces a learning system. Organizations have recognized that learning is also a crucial part of economic growth and hence are plunging money in Competency building programs, start-ups and intrapreneurship.

Objectives

- To identify the current learning practices used in the (IT Industry).
- To investigate on the effectiveness of Learning with different learning methods like Peer Learning, Research learning, Hands on learning, Incidental learning and Project learning.

Literature Review

Cormier-Mac Burnie, et al., (2015) in their research paper show that workplace learning is complex and relational and so is its assessment. Chefs tend to assess the effectiveness of their own workplace learning and that of their subordinates through various means. The dominant measure of effectiveness of learning appears to be linked to the standard paradigm of workplace learning, i.e., the acquisition of knowledge. However, there are also signs that effectiveness of learning is also measured based on the emergent view of workplace learning i.e., that learning is also process as well as product. It also seems that feedback plays an important role in the assessment of chefs' learning and that of their subordinates.

Carla Curado (2014) in her paper explores a new idea presenting the possible relationship between organizational learning and organizational design. There is a diversity of concepts, terminologies and definitions reflecting the embryonic state of the theme's theoretical edification; as a consequence, the development of academic studies that bring rigor to a clear relevant subject is needed. But there is still no common language or unifying paradigm that gathers all those researching in organizational knowledge and organizational learning, so there is the necessity to develop a largely accepted vocabulary able to unite researchers. As a consequence, the strategic theory of the knowledge-based view of the firm is confronted with the limitations and criticisms organizational knowledge and organizational learning still arouse.

Raduan Che Rose et al., (2009) in their paper reveals that there is a relationship between organizational learning organizational commitment, job satisfaction and work performance. However, it is apparent that the integrated relationships between these variables have not been found to be reported. Hence, examines the relationship among these variables using a sample of public service managers in Malaysia.

However a report presented in the year **(2008)** to Canadian Association of Prior Learning assessment, presents a detailed work on learning at workplace learning. The study conducted focuses more on work related informal learning. Many models and articles are discussed in relation to adult learning strategies in workplace. The study was undertaken considering all types of work environments at Canada. There is an important point mentioned about how personal characteristics affect the learning practices at workplace. The study concludes by mentioning about development of policy frame works for learning and development at the work environments.

Michael Eraut (2000) study explores concepts in the area of professional workplace learning and deliberates on formal learning and non-formal learning. A tabular format presented in the paper on typology of non-formal learning gives details on implicit learning, reactive learning and deliberative learning and its impact at the work environments. Beyond all, the important point that is being put forth is that memory structures, knowledge acquisition path ways and linking it to performance. There is also a detailed note discussed on Kolb's experiential learning and implicit learning. The author pens some important point linking tacit knowledge in the professional work environments. The study concludes by putting some concrete points on knowledge acquisition by implicit learning, long term memory, mental schemas, responses, perceptions and norms.

Research Methodology

The present study is included both in exploratory research and descriptive research as it completely focuses on a phenomenon called learning effectiveness, which tries to understand the extent of effectiveness of learning at the work place. The study is completely relying on the primary data. The primary data is collected through structured questionnaire.

Sampling: The sample size taken is 122 respondents. Sampling technique used is convenience sampling. The sample covers IT employees of all ages from many companies at Bengaluru.

Tools used for Analysis: Simple Percentage Analysis, Multiple Correlations and Chi-square tests were used for analyzing the data. The data was fed into IBM SPSS 20 software package for treatment.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	122	100.0
	Excluded	0	0
	Total	122	100.0

Reliability Statistics

Table 2 Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.795	.795	17

The reliability co-efficient is 0.795 the numbers are close to 1. Usually the coefficients should be above 0.7 which are considered as having good internal consistency. Hence the result of the above table (table -2) shows 0.79 is data is reliable.

Demographic Details of the Respondents

Table 3 Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Catagories	No of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	79	65
	Female	43	35
Age	26-30	36	29.5
	31-35	41	33.6
	36-40	26	21.4
	41-45	19	15.5
Monthly Income in Indian Currency (Rs)	51,000-60,000	41	33.6
	61,000-70,000	26	21.3
	71,000-80,000	38	31.1
	81,000 and above	17	14

Education	Graduate	45	36.6
	Post Graduate	56	45.9
	Doctorate	17	13.9
	Others	4	3.6
Marital Status	Married	87	71.3
	Unmarried	35	28.7
No. of Member Earn- ing in the Family	One Member	52	42.6
	Two Members	63	51.6
	Three and more Members	7	5.8

It is evident from the above table (Table 3) demographic details of the respondents that majority of them belong to (79/122) 65 percent are males and the rest 35 (43/122) percent are females. Based on the age classification of the respondents the highest number representation is from 31-35 with 41 and second highest 36 of them belong to the age group of 26-30. The third highest that is 26 of them belong to the age of 36-40. The next category is the income, which is very important as it decides on the capacity and spending of individuals. From the above table it is inferred that income classification almost 33 percent belong to group of Rs 51000-60000 monthly earnings and 31 percent of them belong to the income group of Rs 71000-80000 monthly earnings. The rest of them distributed among Rs 61, 000-70,000 and Rs 81,000 and above.

Chi square Tests Rejected

Table 4 Chi square tests

Variable 1	Variable 2	Chi square Value	P Value	Results
Learning Effectiveness	Project Learning	152.17	.000	Rejected
Learning Effectiveness	Peer Learning	210.02	.000	Rejected
Learning Effectiveness	Research Learning	208.81	.000	Rejected
Learning Effectiveness	Incidental Learning	234.82	.000	Rejected
Learning Effectiveness	Hands on Learning	231.01	.001	Rejected

From the above table it is evident that, there are five variables which was being considered to understand the concept of learning effectiveness. The variables considered includes Project learning, Peer learning, Research Learning, Incidental Learning and Hands-on learning. The hypotheses were formulated and tested with the help of SPSS. The alternate hypothesis were accepted in the all the five cases with the p value of 0.000.

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Project Learning	18.0410	1.80173	122
Peer Learning	18.5082	2.15608	122

Research Learning	18.1721	2.32020	122
Incidental Learning	17.2295	2.46559	122
Hands on Learning	16.8033	2.29854	122

Correlations						
		Project Learning	Peer Learning	Research Learning	Incidental Learning	Hands on learning
	Pearson Correlation	1	.860**	.402**	.294	.132**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.001	.148
	N	122	122	122	122	122
Peer Learning	Pearson Correlation	.860**	1	.149	.331**	.129
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.101	.000	.158
	N	122	122	122	122	122
Research Learning	Pearson Correlation	.402**	.149	1	.276**	.202
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.101		.002	.026
	N	122	122	122	122	122
Incidental Learning	Pearson Correlation	.294**	.331**	.276**	1**	.518**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000	.002		.000
	N	122	122	122	122	122
Hands-on-Learning	Pearson Correlation	.132	.129	.202*	.518	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.148	.158	.026	.000	
	N	122	122	122	122	122

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

As per the above table the correlations factors which is analyzed with all dimensions found to be positive and significant at (1-tailed) and (two tailed). It also shows that the null hypotheses is rejected with all the five dimensions like Project learning, Peer learning, Research Learning, incidental learning and hands on learning. However observing the correlation values it shows high relation in the case of hands on learning.

Discussions

The study presents the five different types of learning that happens at the work environment especially at IT sector. Project Learning, Peer Learning, Research Learning, Incidental learning and Project Learning in the case of these variables the learning effectiveness was tested and the respondents accepted that these kind of learning happens at the workplace and more hands on learning and data also shows close correlation with hands on learning. Moreover learning is a part of assessment of the employees for growth and development. The variables chosen are common modes of learning found in IT sector.

Conclusion

In the year 1990 Senge, Peter published the art and science of learning organization, from then on learning is reiterated in all types of workplaces throughout the world, in order to seek improved work culture and new methods of task performance. The study takes into consideration five variables Project Learning, Peer Learning, Research Learning, Incidental learning and Project Learning. During the data collection the respondent's also reiterated on the point of hands on learning is given more importance at the workplace, which seems to be true as the data reveals the same fact. To conclude the authors would like state that the methods of learning tested, some of them are not included in the appraisal for motivating employees.

Scope for Further Research

This paper mainly focuses on the five variables like Project Learning, Peer Learning, Research Learning, Incidental learning and Project Learning. There are other types of informal learning that happens at the workplace which is not being considered in this study. There is also a bigger scope to capture the other knowledge that has to be codified as a part of formal as well as informal learning. There may be different kinds of learning in other industry sector which is not under the scope of this study.

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